

Supporting Information Figure S1: Respondent characteristics for the questionnaire. (upper right): The age differentiation between questionnaire respondents. (upper left): The differentiation of countries for questionnaire respondents (CZ = Czech Republic, IT = Italy, NL = the Netherlands, DE = Germany, BE = Belgium, UK = United Kingdom, FI = Finland). Czech Republic accounted for most respondents (28), Finland for the least (6). (lower left): the differentiation in gender of questionnaire respondents (M = men, W = women). (lower right): the differentiation of stakeholder types (one respondent could be assigned to two stakeholder groups). Farmers and land owners represented 45.65% of the respondents, researchers 16.30%, farm advisors 13.04% and policy actors 10.87% of the respondents. Stakeholders in the value chain and others accounted for 13.04% of the respondents.

Agroforestry type relevance to stakeholders

Supporting Information Figure S2: The relevance of proposed agroforestry practices according to stakeholders. (upper): Percentage of respondents acknowledging the different proposed types as agroforestry. (lower): Percentage of respondents acknowledging the grouped types of agroforestry according to tool-processing. Czech Republic accounted for most respondents (28), Finland for the least (6). (Hedge = hedgerows, SP = silvopasture, SA = silvoarable, FF = food forest, FG = farm woodland as proxy for forest grazing).

Supporting Information Figure S3: Effects of landscape complexity, composition and configuration on biodiversity levels of different taxonomic groups. 35 effect sizes concerning landscape structure for a comparison of complex landscapes to simple landscapes (i.e., composition: reductions of intensive agriculture, higher percentages of semi-natural habitat, ... and configuration: smaller plot area, better connectivity of seminatural habitats, ...). and functional group as reported or recalculated from subindices in the meta-analyses, representing positive, negative or non-significant results. The underlying effect sizes are based on abundance, diversity and richness metrics and are compared to their baselines (simple landscape agroecosystems). The colors of the dots and silhouettes appoint a taxa's functionality in agricultural context: green = plants, black = soil fauna and microbiota, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species. (a = (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2011), b = (Coutinho et al., 2018), c = (Duarte et al., 2018), d = (Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022), g = (Marja et al., 2022), j = (Shackelford et al., 2013)). Taxa symbols were retrieved from phylopic.org.

Supporting Information Figure S4: Tool construction preferences according to questionnaire respondents. This question addressed both input types separately and as combination. A fourth 'open' option enabled respondents to give other answers (e.g., 'nothing').

Supporting Information Figure S5: Underlying variables for the Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling (stress = 0.196). (WT = webttool, S = spreadsheet, GIS = geographic information system-tool, R = programming tool, TG = guidelines, CP = computer program, F = farm scale, L = landscape/regional scale, P = plot/field scale, Hedge = hedgerows, AF = agroforestry, SP = silvopasture, SA = silvoarable, FF = food forest, FG = forest grazing, Woody = implementation of woody features basic characterization, FarmChar = checklist of farm characteristics, Maps = habitat/environment mapping, BioChar = checklist for biotic indicators, LndscpCompl = landscape structure, MetricBio = one global metric for overall biodiversity, MetricSpGr = one or more metrics for specific species groups, EffAF = effects of different species groups, PropAct = proposed actions towards improving biodiversity, SciTransp = scientific transparency, Free_av = freely availability, RelevanceEU = relevance to European scope).